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RESIDUAL CURRENT DEVICES (RCD) AND ITS APPLICATIONS

Abstract: On the basis of regulatory documents, recommendations for ensuring power supply and features of its solution are given. A full-fledged life of modern society is unthinkable without the use of electric energy. The resulting interruptions of electricity supply to one degree or another paralyze the life of society, generating negative consequences that do not depend on the time frame and type of activity of members of society. All this determines the special importance of the problem of reliable power supply.

The article can be used by specialists and designers to make design decisions and develop measures for power supply.

Keywords: power supply; electrical networks; electrical safety; electrical equipment.

First, let's see why you need to install an RCD or a difautomat in your homes or electrical installations?

It all depends on what you will use it for.

The main purposes of the use of RCD:

- protection of people from electric shock
- prevention of fire due to leakage current of electrical wiring

Figure 1. The appearance of a single-phase (two-pole) RCD.

The use of RCD to protect people from electric shock.

When used for personal purposes, such electrical appliances as a microwave oven, an electric stove, a water heater, a computer and others, there is a possibility of

electric shock, because these household appliances primarily have a metal housing (conducts electric current) and a complex internal circuit.

Due to various influences (mechanical, thermal, etc.), as well as due to the long service life, the insulation of the wires of these household appliances may become unusable.

This applies not only to electrical appliances, but also to cable wiring lines.

If the insulation of the conductor is violated, there is a possibility of shorting this wire to the metal body of an electrical device. At the same time, a phase appears on the housing, or in other words, a potential equal to the mains voltage. But this will occur if there is no grounding of the housing.

Without application in the RCD scheme

If you simultaneously touch an electrical appliance, and in our house damaged insulation, and any other object connected to the ground, for example, with a sink or battery, then you may be electrocuted.

1. The consequences of such a "touch" can be very different. In one case, this is a "slight fright", in the other — serious consequences, up to cardiac arrest from the passage of current through the human body. Read, here are some real-life examples:

- a serious accident with an electrician on a 0.4 (kV) shield
- an accident with an electrician in RU-0.4 (kV)
- a fatal accident on RP-10 (kV)
- a group accident on GRU-10 (kV)

The use of RCD in a circuit with a protective conductor

To prevent such consequences in case of violation of the insulation of devices or cables, it is necessary to use a protective shutdown device (RCD).

Figure 2. The use of RCD in a circuit with a protective conductor.

And here such a situation will not happen, because when the phase conductor is closed to the metal body of an electrical device, a current will appear at which the RCD or circuit breaker will work.

This will happen if you use electrical wiring with a protective conductor PE (phase, zero, ground), i.e. the TN-C-S or TN-S system.

The use of RCD to prevent the occurrence of fire

In case of improper or substandard installation of electrical wiring, as well as the use of electrical wires or cables with faulty insulation, RCD is used to prevent a fire in the event of a current leak.

For these purposes, a protective shutdown device (RCD) with a setpoint of 300-500 (mA) is used. Such a setpoint is taken from the preliminary calculation of thermal power.

With a leakage current of 500 (mA), the thermal power released in this section of the circuit is approximately 100 (W). This power is sufficient to ignite materials (wood, plastic, paper) located at the fault site.

Conclusion

Electrical safety of electrical installations can be ensured by: selecting electrical equipment of the appropriate design; using methods and means of

protection against electric shock; performing organizational and technical measures.

The direction of further research is the recommendations for the use of RCD and differential circuit breakers manufactured by the industry in order to increase the electrical safety of low-voltage electrical installations of a certain power.

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